

ON THE PHOTOCHEMICAL OXIDATION OF ORGANIC SUBSTANCES BY HYDROGEN PEROXIDE IN ACID MEDIUM WITH INORGANIC SOLS AS PHOTOSENSITISER.

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In some unpublished papers from this laboratory, photochemical reactions have been studied with the following sols as photosensitisers :— Tungstic acid sol and ferric hydroxide sol. As oxidants were used iodine, potassium indigo-tetrasulphonate and methylene blue.

These oxidants have generally absorption for radiations of $366 \mu\mu$ and in determining the amount of effective intensity of radiation absorbed by the photosensitising sol alone, indirect methods of calculation had to be employed. The use of hydrogen peroxide as an oxidant removed this defect as it has comparatively small absorption at $366 \mu\mu$. By carrying out experiments on photo-oxidation only in the range of $p_x 1.5-4.8$, the spontaneous decomposition of H_2O_2 was avoided. The use of hydrogen peroxide has also the advantage, that its concentration at any time during the progress of the reaction can be accurately estimated volumetrically.

It is well known that hydrogen peroxide reacts with tungstic acid, molybdic acid, vanadic acid and chromic acid sols to form pertungstates, permolybdates, pervanadates and perchromates.

Brode (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1901, 37, 299) observed that pertungstic acid remains fairly dissociated in solution. But quantitative data about the equilibrium constant was supplied by Pissarjewsky (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1903, 13, 167), who determined the free H_2O_2 in aqueous solution by partition experiments with ether.

In experiment with $0.05M-Na_2WO_4$ and $0.097M-H_2O_2$ (in $0.125M H_2SO_4$), the concentration as bound H_2O_2 was found by Pissarjewsky (*loc. cit.*) to be 0.0385% . So the concentrations of H_2O_2 and free tungstic acid sol are $0.0385M$ and $0.0115M$ respectively. Therefore the equilibrium constant

$$K = \frac{(0.0585) \times (0.0115)}{(0.0385)} = 1.75 \times 10^{-2}$$

With the help of this equilibrium constant, we can calculate the bound H_2O_2 in mixtures of different concentrations of H_2O_2 and tungstic acid

sol. In Table I are given the concentrations of bound H_2O_2 when the concentration of tungstate is $0.025 M$ and that of H_2O_2 between $0.0112 M$ to $0.0557 M$, as was the case in our experiments on photocatalytic reaction with the system.

TABLE I.

Conc. of tungstate (M) ...	0.025	0.025	0.025	0.025	0.025	0.025
Conc. of H_2O_2 (M) ...	0.0112	0.017	0.0261	0.0353	0.038	0.0557
Conc. of bound H_2O_2 (M)...	0.00585	0.00830	0.01141	0.0138	0.01437	0.01719

It is evident from the above table that when the initial concentration of H_2O_2 is low, the concentration of bound H_2O_2 in the mixture is proportional to the initial concentration of H_2O_2 , while at higher initial concentration of H_2O_2 , the concentration of bound H_2O_2 remains practically unaffected by the change in the initial concentration of H_2O_2 .

It is clear therefore that in a mixture containing a tungstate, hydrochloric acid and H_2O_2 , we have free hydrogen peroxide, pertungstic acid and micelles of tungstic acid sol; and it is very probable that the molecules of pertungstic acid is adsorbed on the surface of these micelles. The process of photocatalysis may be depicted as follows:—

The mechanism of photo-oxidation is similar in the case of other sols, but quantitative data on the equilibrium between the acid sol, peracid and hydrogen peroxide are not available.

Permolybdates have been described by Pechard, Pissarjewsky and others. Owing to dissociation and *formation of colloidal complexes*, the results are not reliable. The general results therefore show that there are two permolybdic acids, permonomolybdic acid (MoO_3, H_2O_2 and H_2MoO_5) and perdimolybdic acid ($MoO_3, 2H_2O_2$ or H_4MoO_6).

Pervanadic Acid.—Meyer and co-workers (*Z. anal. Chem.*, 1926, 69, 1520) found that V_2O_5 dissolves in H_2O_2 giving a pale yellow solution, which appears to contain vanadic acid in a colloidal form; at the same time H_2O_2 is catalytically decomposed.

Vanadic Acid Sol.—We have found that in presence of sufficient acetic acid, the vanadic acid sol prepared by the action of acetic acid on

sodium vanadate does not decompose hydrogen peroxide and is not coagulated during the process of oxidation of glucose.

According to Canneri (*Gazzetta*, 1926, 58, 11,779), the electrical conductivity of solutions of sodium metavanadate acidified with increasing quantities of acetic acid varies continuously at 30°, indicating that condensation of molecules of metavanadate is a continuous function of the concentration of acetic acid.

Dumanski in a series of papers has established the point of view that with progressive increase in the number of atoms of vanadium in a molecule of vanadic acid, the colloid-chemical properties become more and more manifest.

Perchromic Acid.—When hydrogen peroxide is added to chromic hydroxide, per-compounds are formed (Barreswil, *Ann. chim. phys.*, 1848, iii, 20, 364). When the concentration of hydrogen peroxide and chromic acid is very high, the per-salt decomposes liberating oxygen. But in very dilute solutions, when the concentration of hydrogen peroxide is less than that of chromic acid, we found that the per-salt is stable and no decomposition was observed for 8 hours in a quartz vessel (*vide* Section F).

Experimental Arrangement.—The source of light was a point source quartz mercury lamp which was run from a battery of 30 volts. An ammeter in circuit and a variable external resistance were used to keep the strength of current at values between 2 and 2.6 amperes.

For isolating monochromatic radiations at 366 μ , Schott and Gen ultra-violet filter No. 312 was used. In the case of red light, a thousand c.p. point-o-lite Edison Lamp was used with suitable filters. Wave-length 579 μ was isolated with the help of Zeiss monochromators.

Light from the lamp was rendered parallel by a quartz lens placed at its focal distance from the lamp and passed into the reaction vessel, kept inside a double jacketed box through a window of fused quartz plate. The temperature was kept constant within 0.1° by circulating water from a thermostat through the annular space of the box. The reaction vessel was a rectangular stoppered cell made of plane parallel plates of fused transparent silica.

No cement was used, the rectangular joints being fused to one another. The closed stopper was very well ground into a circular aperture in the thick top plate of the reaction cell.

The intensity of incident radiation was varied by using quartz lenses of different focal lengths. The method of measuring intensities actually absorbed by the reaction mixture consisted in first observing the deflection in a Moll galvanometer with a Moll surface thermopile, covered with a quartz

window and placed immediately behind the reaction cell which contained only water. The deflection was next noted when the cell was filled with the reaction mixture. The difference gave the quantity of radiant energy absorbed by the reacting system. The thermopile recording system was frequently calibrated by means of a Standard incandescent lamp, tested by the National Bureau of Standards, Washington. The scattering power for light was found very small in the case of the sols (unpublished work by Ghosh and Banerjee).

In experiments with hydrogen peroxide, cleanliness must be scrupulously observed, it being very unstable in presence of dust particles. In these experiments most of the apparatus, including the Pyrex titrating vessels, were steamed one day before the time for carrying out an experiment and kept in a glass case. All the apparatus were not allowed to come in contact with any solid substance except glass. One glass hooked pipette stand was made for the purpose.

All extra-pure chemicals (Merck or Kahlbaum) were used in these experiments. Hydrogen peroxide used was Merck's Reagent 'Perhydrol' stocked in paraffined bottle. The rate of reaction was followed by estimating the decrease in the concentration of hydrogen peroxide with time. For estimating hydrogen peroxide, the well known standard method of Kingzett (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1880, 792) was adopted. 0.2—0.3 C.c. of reaction mixture was taken for each titration with a micropipette. The iodine liberated was estimated with standard thiosulphate (generally 0.01*N*) from a microburette, reading direct to 0.01 c.c., using freshly prepared starch solution as internal indicator. On performing the blank experiments with redistilled water, sulphuric acid and potassium iodide at 80° the temperature at which the estimation was carried, it was seen that iodine liberated in 15 minutes is practically nil. It must be mentioned here that throughout these series of experiments, redistilled water was used for preparing all the solutions. The hydrogen peroxide was freshly prepared before each day's experiment as it decomposes in glass vessel after standing for some time (about 10-12 hours). It is stable in quartz vessel for a much longer time. For measuring temperature coefficient, maximum temperature used was 37° 5, as above this temperature, hydrogen peroxide becomes unstable and gives erratic results.

A. The Photochemical Oxidation of Glucose by Hydrogen Peroxide in Acid Medium with Tungstic Acid Sol as Photosensitiser.

In presence of light, hydrogen peroxide cannot oxidise glucose in

acid solution but when some photosensitiser, e.g., tungstic acid sol is added to the system, oxidation commences.

A mixture of glucose, hydrogen peroxide, hydrochloric acid, and sodium tungstate does not react when kept in the dark for a sufficiently long time (14 hours).

The unimolecular velocity constant was calculated by the formula $K = 2.3 \times 1/t \log (a/a-x)$ where t is reckoned in seconds. The zero-molecular velocity constant K_0 is given by the number of g. mols. transformed in 1 second in a unit cell (1 cm. $\times$ 1 cm. $\times$ 1 cm.).

TABLE IIa.

Effect of varying the concentration of hydrogen peroxide.

Wave-length = 366 μ m. Temp. of thermostat = 32° 5. Strength of thio-sulphate = 0.01N. H_2O_2 = 0.017M. Conc. of sodium tungstate = 0.025M. Conc. of HCl = 0.0783N. Conc. of glucose = 0.025M. Intensity of absorbed radiation = 2030 ergs per sq. cm. per sec.

Time.	Pertungstate.	C.c. thiosulphate = 0.232 c.c. reac- tion mixture.	K_{unimol} with respect to H_2O_2 = $2.3 \times 1/t_{sec} \log a/a-x$.
0 min.		0.755	
60	0.0071M	0.655	5.36×10^{-5} (Induction period)
120	0.0054	0.475	8.92×10^{-5} (between 283)
180	0.0040	0.345	8.90×10^{-5} (between 284)
			Mean 8.92×10^{-5}

TABLE IIb.

Conc. of hydrogen peroxide = 0.0353M. Other factors same as before.

Time.	Pertungstate.	C.c. thiosulphate = 0.232 c.c. reac- tion mixture.	K_0 (zeromolecular with res- pect to H_2O_2 , expressed in g. mols. transformed per sec. in a unit cell).
0 min.		1.64	
60	0.0133M	1.54	
120	0.0122	1.35	12.0×10^{-10}
182	0.0111	1.16	11.8×10^{-10}
			Mean 11.9×10^{-10}

TABLE III.

Tungstate = 0.025*M*. Glucose = 0.025*M*. Intensity of absorbed radiation = 2030 ergs per sq. cm. per sec. Thiosulphate = 0.01*N*. *d* (thickness of reaction cell) = 1 cm. Conc. of HCl added = 0.0783*N*.

H ₂ O ₂ .	Per-tungstate.	K _{unimol} × 10 ⁵ .	K ₀ × 10 ¹⁰ .	γ (quantum efficiency).
0.0112 <i>M</i>	0.00585 <i>M</i>	9.04		1.40
0.017	0.00830	8.92		1.50
0.0353	0.0138		11.90	1.92
0.038	0.01437		11.90	1.92
0.0557	0.01719		12.41	1.97

TABLE IV.

Sodium tungstate = 0.025*M*. HCl added = 0.0766*N*. Intensity of absorbed radiation same as in Table II.

Glucose.	H ₂ O ₂ .	Per-tungstate.	K _{unimol} × 10 ⁵ .	K ₀ × 10 ¹⁰ .
0.0063 <i>M</i>	0.0174 <i>M</i>	0.00845 <i>M</i>	8.44	
"	0.034	0.0135		12.02
0.05	0.0172	0.00835	9.13	
"	0.0373	0.0142		12.63

It will be noticed from Tables II and III that the reaction follows the unimolecular law when the concentration of hydrogen peroxide is low, but at very high concentration of hydrogen peroxide the reaction is zero-molecular. In this respect, it resembles the heterogeneous gaseous reactions. The concentration of hydrogen peroxide is without any appreciable influence on the unimolecular or the zero-molecular velocity constants.

There is a considerable period of induction at the beginning of the reaction and this increases with the increase in the concentration of hydrogen peroxide.

TABLE V.

Effect of varying the concentration of glucose.

Intensity of absorbed radiation per sq. cm. per sec. = 2030 ergs.

Glucose.	H ₂ O ₂ .	HCl added.	Conc. of tungstate.	K _{unimol} × 10 ⁵ .
0.05 M	0.0172 M	0.0766 N	0.025 M	9.13
0.025	0.017	"	"	8.92
0.0063	0.0174	"	"	8.44

FIG. 1.

Though $1/c$ plotted against $1/K$ gives us approximately a straight line (Fig. 1), the variation in K with concentration of glucose is so small that the velocity constant may be taken as practically independent of the concentration of glucose.

Effect of Varying the p_H of the Reacting System.—The p_H of the system was kept constant with citrate buffer. It was found that citrate buffer did not react with hydrogen peroxide in presence of sol even in the ultraviolet light. It must be mentioned here that citrate buffer was found to inhibit the spontaneous decomposition of hydrogen peroxide even when the concentration of hydrochloric acid in the reaction mixture was very low. The hydrogen ion concentration of the reaction mixture was determined electrometrically using a quinhydrone electrode.

TABLE VI.

Sodium tungstate = 0.025 M. H₂O₂ = 0.017 M. Glucose = 0.025 M.
Thiosulphate = 0.01 N.

HCl added.	p_H of reaction mixture.	Energy absorbed in ergs/sq.cm./sec.	K _{unimol} × 10 ⁵ .
0.0318 N	4.78	1843	2.37
0.0366	3.07	2500	9.36
0.0414	2.39	2580	10.07
0.0462	2.11	2580	7.89
0.0510	1.94	2580	7.41
0.0558	1.83	2580	6.90

The velocity of reaction at first increases rapidly with the decrease in the p_H value of the reacting system, reaches a maximum value and then decreases with the further decrease in the p_H value of the system. The reaction is minimum when the concentration of HCl added is nearly 1.5 times the concentration of sodium tungstate.

TABLE VII.

Effect of varying the intensity of absorbed radiation.

d (thickness of the reaction cell) = 1 cm. Glucose = 0.025M.
Tungstate = 0.025M.

* I_{abs} .	HCl added.	H ₂ O ₂ .	$K_{\text{unimol}} \times 10^5$.	$K_0 \times 10^{10}$.
(a) 2030	0.0783 N	0.038 N	—	11.91
919	0.0766	0.0384	—	8.27
(b) 2030	0.0783	0.017	8.92	—
919	0.0766	0.0172	6.02	—

The velocity constants vary as the square root of the absorbed radiation.

Temperature Coefficient.—The temperature coefficient is small, being of the order of 1.1–1.2.

Quantum Efficiency of the Process.—The calculation of two typical examples are given below. The dimension of quartz cell in this case was 1.8 cm. $\times$ 1.8 cm. $\times$ 1 cm.

Example 1. Here the velocity constant is unimolecular.

In Table IIa, the intensity of absorbed radiation per sq. cm. per sec. by a column of solution 1 cm. thick

$$= 2030 \text{ ergs} = \frac{2030 \times 3.66 \times 10^{-7}}{(6.55 \times 10^{-27}) \times (3 \times 10^{10}) \times (6.1 \times 10^{23})} \text{ Einstein} \\ = 6.20 \times 10^{-10} \text{ Einstein.}$$

Again the number of g. mols. transformed in unit time in a unit cell (1 cm. $\times$ 1 cm. $\times$ 1 cm.) (taking readings for 120 minutes after the induction period was over)

$$= \frac{0.31}{0.232} \times 0.01 \\ = \frac{0.31}{2 \times 1000 \times 120 \times 60} = 9.87 \times 10^{-10}.$$

Quantum efficiency of the process

$$= \frac{\text{No. of g. mols. transformed}}{\text{No. of Einsteins absorbed}} = \frac{2.87 \times 10^{-10}}{6.2 \times 10^{-10}} = 1.59.$$

* In this and other tables that follow, I_{abs} signifies intensity of absorbed radiation in ergs/sq. cm./sec.

Example 2. Here the velocity constant is zero-molecular (Table IIb).

Intensity of absorbed radiation = 6.2×10^{-10} Einstein (as before).
 No. of g. mols. transformed in 1 sec. in a unit cell

$$= K_0 = \frac{11.91 \times 10^{-10}}{1}$$

$$\text{Quantum efficiency} = \frac{11.91 \times 10^{-10}}{6.2 \times 10^{-10}} = 1.92.$$

The mechanism of reaction in the present case, when tungstic acid sol acts only as photocatalyst with H_2O_2 as oxidant and glucose as reductant, is materially different from that of the photo-reaction when tungstic acid sol itself was the active oxidising agent. There the reaction was always zero-molecular and the velocity of reaction was proportional to the intensity of radiation absorbed.

In this case, however, the following characteristic features are observed :—

(1) For relatively high concentration of H_2O_2 , the reaction is zero-molecular with respect to H_2O_2 but for lower concentration of H_2O_2 it is unimolecular.

(2) The velocity of reaction is proportional to the square root of the intensity of absorbed radiation.

(3) The quantum efficiency is generally greater than unity calculated on the assumption that the whole of the absorbed radiation is available for photo-activation.

(4) The inverse of the velocity constant plotted against the inverse of the concentration of the reductant is a straight line.

The following mechanism explains all these characteristics.

The whole of the absorbed radiation is assumed to be effective for purposes of photochemical transformation.

A quantum of absorbed radiation decomposes a molecule of pertungstic acid thus :—

The stationary concentration of O atom is given by

$$\frac{I}{h\nu} = K_3[O]^2 + K_4[O_2 \text{ active}] C_o^* + K_2[O] C_{s[pr]}$$

where $C_{s[pr]}$ is the surface concentration of pertungstate and C_o^* is the surface concentration of glucose.

Reactions (4) and (2) have practically the same velocity.

$$\text{Hence, } [O] = \sqrt{\frac{I}{K_3 h\nu}}.$$

The stationary concentration of O_2 active is given by

$$K_2[O]C_{s[pr]} = K_3[O_2 \text{ active}] + K_4[O_2 \text{ active}] C_o^*$$

$$\text{or } [O_2] \text{ (active)} = \frac{K_2 \left[\frac{I}{K_3 h\nu} \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} C_{s[pr]}}{K_3 + K_4 C_o^*}$$

Hence the velocity of oxidation of glucose is given by (4)

$$\begin{aligned} \text{and is } &= \sqrt{\frac{I}{K_3 h\nu}} \cdot K_2 C_{s[pr]} \cdot \frac{K_4 C_o^*}{K_3 + K_4 C_o^*} \\ &= \sqrt{\frac{I}{K_3 h\nu}} \cdot K_2 \cdot \frac{K' C_{pr} \text{ (Bulk)}}{K'' + K' C_{pr} \text{ (Bulk)}} \cdot \frac{K_4 C_o^*}{K_3 + K_4 C_o^*}. \end{aligned}$$

It is probable that the absorptive capacity of tungstic acid micelles for pertungstic acid molecules will be very large, so that practically all the latter molecules may exist in the surface phase. Even then, it would be expected, as already pointed out, that the concentration of pertungstic acid will be proportional to the concentration of H_2O_2 at low concentrations of the latter; hence in this region we should observe unimolecular velocity

constants; but when concentration of H_2O_2 is large, C_{PT} (Bulk) remains practically constant and we get zero-molecular velocity constants.

Again according to Langmuir,

$$C_G^S = \frac{K_6 C_B^R}{K_7 + K_6 C_B^R}$$

where C_B^R is the bulk concentration of the reductant.

When C_B^R is very large, $K_7 + K_6 C_B^R$ may be taken practically equal to $K_6 C_B^R$, and we have dx/dt practically independent of C_B^R under otherwise identical conditions, as has been experimentally found to be the case.

B. Induction Period.

The photochemical oxidation of glucose by hydrogen peroxide in acid medium with ordinary tungstic acid sol as photosensitiser is attended with a large period of induction. Some typical data are shown in Table VIII.

TABLE VIII.

<i>I</i> _{abs.}	Glucose.	HCl.	H ₂ O ₂ .	Tungstate.	Period of induction.
(a) 2030	0.025M	0.0783N	0.038M	0.025M	29 min.
919	„	0.0766	0.0384	„	53
(b) 2030	„	0.0783	0.020	„	25
919	„	0.0766	„	„	41

Period of induction increases as the intensity of absorbed radiation decreases.

The influence of various variables, *e.g.*, concentration of reactants, intensity of radiation, etc., on the period of induction was studied and the observations may be summarised thus:—

(i) The induction period suddenly becomes very great when the molar conc. of hydrogen peroxide exceeds the concentration of sodium tungstate.

(ii) The induction period increases as the p_n of the system decreases.

(iii) The induction period decreases as the intensity of absorbed radiation increases.

Photo-reaction with Pre-excited Tungstic Acid Sol.—Here tungstic acid sol was first exposed to ultraviolet light for a sufficiently long time (about 3 hours) and then mixed with other components of the reacting system. The results are given below.

TABLE IX.

(a) Glucose = 0.025M. HCl = 0.08N. H_2O_2 = 0.0158. Sodium tungstate = 0.025M. Temp. = 32°.5. Thiosulphate = 0.01N. $d = 0.5$ cm.

Intensity of absorbed radiation = 461 ergs per sq. cm. per sec.

Time.	C.c. thiosulphate = 0.232 c.c. reaction mixture.	$K_{unimol} \times 10^5$.
0 min	0.73	...
58	0.625	4.44
118	0.54	4.26
		Mean 4.37

(b) H_2O_2 = 0.029N. $d = 0.5$ cm. Other factors same as in (a).

Time.	C.c. thiosulphate = 0.232 c.c. reaction mixture.	$K_0 \times 10^{10}$ (No. of g. mols. transformed in 1 sec. in a unit cell).
0 min.	1.34	...
57	1.20	8.80
130	1.02	8.84
		Mean 8.82

The induction period observed before disappeared when the sol was matured by exposure to the effective radiation before it is mixed with the other components of the reacting system. Here again the velocity constant is unimolecular when the concentration of H_2O_2 is low and at higher concentration of hydrogen peroxide it is zeromolecular. The concentration of hydrogen peroxide is without any appreciable influence on the

unimolecular or the zero-molecular velocity constants, and under similar conditions of experiment the velocities observed are nearly the same as in Section A.

TABLE X.

Effect of varying the concentration of hydrogen peroxide

Intensity of absorbed radiation = 950 ergs per sq. cm./per sec. $d = 0.5$ cm.
Sodium tungstate = 0.025M. HCl added = 0.08N.

Glucose (M)	0.0125	0.0125	0.0125	0.0125	0.0125	0.025	0.025	0.025	0.0063	0.0063
H ₂ O ₂ .	0.011	0.014	0.0157	0.0284	0.0343	0.0118	0.015	0.028	0.0112	0.029
K _{unimol} × 10 ⁵	6.56	6.21	6.51			6.51	6.56		6.26	
K ₀ × 10 ¹⁰				12.56	12.61			12.52		12.40

TABLE XI.

Effect of varying the concentration of glucose.

Glucose.	Tungstate.	H ₂ O ₂ .	HCl.	K _{unimol} × 10 ⁵ .
0.025M	0.025M	0.011M	0.08N	6.56
0.0125	"	0.0118	"	6.51
0.0063	"	0.0112	"	6.26

The velocity constant is practically independent of the concentration of glucose.

TABLE XII.

Variation of the intensity of absorbed radiation.

I _{abs.}	Glucose.	Tungstate.	H ₂ O ₂ .	HCl.	K _{unimol} × 10 ⁵ .	K ₀ × 10 ¹⁰ .
(a) 950	0.025M	0.025M	0.0157M	0.08N	6.51	
461	"	"	0.0159	"	4.18	
(b) 950	"	"	0.0284	"		12.56
461	"	"	0.0288	"		8.84

The velocity constants vary as the square root of absorbed radiation.

Effect of Varying the p_{H} of the System.—The p_{H} of the system was kept constant with citrate buffer as in the previous section. No reaction was found between citrate buffer and hydrogen peroxide in presence of pre-excited tungstic acid sol in the ultraviolet.

TABLE XIII.

Glucose.	Tungstate.	H ₂ O ₂ .	p_{H} .	$K_{\text{unimol}} \times 10^6$.
0.025M	0.025M	0.0180M	6.39	1.20
"	"	0.0180	5.41	2.35
"	"	0.0145	4.41	7.82
"	"	0.0140	1.17	7.36
"	"	0.0145	1.13	6.44

The mechanism of reaction is the same as that with unpre-excited tungstic acid sol.

C. Photo-oxidation of Formaldehyde and Lævulose.

The reaction is more or less similar to the oxidation of glucose by hydrogen peroxide in acid medium with tungstic acid sol as photo-catalyst with some exceptions. Neither of these reactions had any induction period. There is no dark reaction in both the cases. The velocity of reaction obeyed unimolecular law for low concentrations of hydrogen peroxide. The influence of the nature of polarisation of the exciting light was studied. Formaldehyde was standardised by estimating with iodine and sodium thio-sulphate (*vide* Plimner, "Practical Organic and Bio-chemistry" p. 85). Pfanstiel's lævulose was used for the reaction.

TABLE XIV.

(a) H₂O₂ = 0.02M. Tungstate = 0.025M. HCl = 0.0877N. Formaldehyde = 0.0362M. Thiosulphate = 0.01N. Temp. = 22°. $I_{\text{abs.}} = 1930.6$ ergs.

Time.	C.c. thiosulphate ≡ 0.3 c.c. of the reaction mixture.	K_{unimol} with respect to H ₂ O ₂ .	K_{mean} .	Quantum efficiency.
0 min.	1.42	—		
60	1.29	2.85×10^{-8}		
120	1.16	2.92×10^{-8}	2.85×10^{-8}	1.02
210	1.00	2.76×10^{-8}		

(b) $H_2O_2 = 0.02M$. Tungstate = $0.025M$. $HCl = 0.078N$. Lævulose = $0.025M$. Thiosulphate = $0.01N$. Temp. = 22° . $I_{abs.} = 1931$ ergs.

Time.	C.c. thiosulphate = 0.3 c.c. of the reaction mixture.	K_{unimol} with respect to H_2O_2 .	K_{mean} .	Quantum efficiency.
0 min.	1.190			
60	0.925	7.02×10^{-5}	6.97×10^{-5}	2.05
140	0.660	7.02×10^{-5}		
240	0.440	6.90×10^{-5}		

From the above table it is quite evident that neither of the reactions has any period of induction.

TABLE XV.

Effect of varying the intensity of absorbed radiation.

$\lambda = 366\mu$. Temp. = 22° . Conc. of tungstate = $0.25M$. Conc. of $H_2O_2 = 0.02M$.

$I_{abs.}$	Reductants.	HCl added.	$K_{unimol} \times 10^5$.
(a) 1931 ergs	H·CHO ($0.036M$)	$0.0877N$	2.85
668	" "	"	1.17
(b) 1931	Lævulose ($0.025M$)	$0.078N$	6.97
772	" "	"	4.03

The velocity constant under otherwise similar conditions varies as the square root of the intensity of radiation absorbed.

The mechanism of reaction is the same as with glucose as the reductant.

D. Influence of Promoters.

No photochemical oxidation of glucose in presence of a promoter only, in absence of tungstic acid sol, was observed. Sol, pre-activated for 3 hours was used in each experiment and thereby the induction period was avoided. The results are given below.

TABLE XVI.

$\lambda = 366\mu\mu$. Temp. of thermostat = 31° . Glucose = $0.025M$. Tungstate = $0.025M$.

Promoter used.	Conc. of promoter.	I_{abs} .	H_2O_2 .	Conc. of acid added.	Constant with promoter.	Constant without promoter under otherwise identical conditions.
$FeCl_3, 6H_2O$	$M/10,000$	696 ergs.	$0.034M$	$0.08N$	19.64×10^{-10} (zeromol)	10.91×10^{-10} (zeromol)
"	"	"	0.0287	"	13.81×10^{-10} (zero)	10.91×10^{-10} (zero)
"	"	"	0.0136	"	5.59×10^{-5} (uni)	3.96×10^{-5} (uni)
"	"	"	0.0110	"	5.75×10^{-5} (uni)	3.96×10^{-5} (uni)
"	$M/5000$	1513	0.0348	$0.1175N$	22.18×10^{-10} (zero)	14.68×10^{-10} (zero)
"	"	"	0.0286	"	17.36×10^{-10} (zero)	14.68×10^{-10} (zero)
"	"	"	0.0146	"	8.58×10^{-5} (uni)	7.43×10^{-5} (uni)
"	"	"	0.0091	"	10.99×10^{-5} (uni)	7.43×10^{-5} (uni)
$FeSO_4, 7H_2O$	$M/20,000$	2980	0.0123	"	15.34×10^{-5} (uni)	10.97×10^{-5} (uni)
$CuSO_4, 6H_2O$	"	"	0.0131	"	15.76×10^{-5} (uni)	10.97×10^{-5} (uni)
Manganese citrate	"	"	0.131	"	14.42×10^{-5} (uni)	10.97×10^{-5} (uni)

As in the experiments without a promoter, here also the velocity of reaction obeys the unimolecular law when the concentration of hydrogen peroxide is low and is zeromolecular when the concentration of hydrogen peroxide is high.

The general mechanism of promoter action is not known with certainty. The promoter may (i) increase the number of active points on the catalyst surface,—the area of the surface round about the promoter atom being more reactive; (ii) may prevent the destruction of the active point during the course of reaction; (iii) may retard the transformation of active intermediate reactants into normal inactive forms.

In the photochemical reactions which we have studied, the reaction is initiated by the absorption of a quantum of radiation and hence hypotheses (i) and (ii) about regarding promoter actions are not applicable.

The promoters somehow retard reaction (3) in conversion of O_2 (active) into O_2 (normal) or reaction (5), *i. e.*, conversion of two oxygen atoms into a molecule of oxygen (*vide* Section A, discussion).

Yoshimera (*J. Soc. Chem. Ind. Japan*, 1934, 37, 350) explained the promoter action of Cr_2O_3 in $Fe_2O_3-Cr_2O_3$ catalyst in the production

of hydrogen by means of water gas reaction by assuming that Cr_2O_3 retards the movements of active atoms to inactive positions.

E. Chromic Tungstate as Photosensitiser.

Tungstic acid sol absorbs only ultraviolet light whereas chromic tungstate sol, in addition to general absorption in the ultraviolet, has absorption bands in the yellow and the red. The present investigation was undertaken to study the above photo-oxidation in details in light of different wave-lengths.

Preparation of Chromic Tungstate Sol.—The sol was prepared after Dhar and Prakash (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 7, 367).

Estimation of Tungstic Acid in Chromic Tungstate Sol.—Tungstic acid in chromic tungstate was estimated by precipitating the tungstic acid with the help of hydrochloric acid and cinchonine hydrochloride (*cf.* Treadwell and Hall, "Analytical Chemistry", 1924, Vol. II, p. 268) and igniting the precipitate as WO_3 .

In this paper the molar concentration of chromic tungstate is expressed in terms of WO_3 .

For red light, a point-o-lite lamp of 1000 c. p. run at a constant current of 5 amperes was used.

TABLE XVII.

Effect of varying the concentration of hydrogen peroxide.

Region = 750–600 $\mu\mu$. $d = 1$ cm. Glucose = 0.025M. HCl = 0.562N.

I_{445} .	H_2O_2 .	Chromic tungstate.	K_0 (No. of g. mol. transformed per sec in a unit cell) (P).	$\frac{P}{Q} \times 10^{12}$.	Quantum efficiency.
4500 ergs.	0.0173M	0.02052M	13.79×10^{-10}	3.06	0.54
"	0.0182	"	13.49×10^{-10}	3.00	0.53
"	0.0183	"	13.79×10^{-10}	3.06	0.54
"	0.0235	"	13.19×10^{-10}	2.91	0.52
"	0.0252	"	13.49×10^{-10}	3.00	0.53
3500 ergs.	0.0099	0.01231M	10.49×10^{-10}	3.00	0.53
"	0.0128	"	10.79×10^{-10}	3.08	0.54
"	0.0175	"	10.40×10^{-10}	2.97	0.57
"	0.0183	"	10.49×10^{-10}	3.00	0.53
"	0.0212	"	10.79×10^{-10}	3.08	0.54

TABLE XVIII.

Region = $366\mu\mu$. $I_{\text{abs.}} = 2030 \text{ ergs} = 6.2 \times 10^{-10} \text{ Einstein}$. Glucose = $0.025M$.
 HCl = $0.39N$. Chronic tungstate = $0.0082N$.

H_2O_2 .	$K_{\text{unimol}} \times 10^5$.	$K_0 \times 10^{10}$.	Quantum efficiency.
0.0121 M	5.01	...	0.9
0.023	5.01	...	1.7
0.0374	...	5.04	0.815
0.0463	...	4.92	0.80
0.0489	...	4.92	0.80
0.0560	...	5.01	0.81
0.0740	...	5.04	0.815

From Table VIII it will be seen that in the region $750-600\mu\mu$, the reaction always obeys the zeromolecular law but when the region ($366\mu\mu$) is used as the exciting radiation (Table VIII), the reaction is monomolecular at low concentrations of hydrogen peroxide but at high concentrations of hydrogen peroxide, the reaction is zeromolecular (*cf.* Tables XVII and XVIII).

In the region $750-600\mu\mu$, the velocity constant is proportional to the intensity of absorbed radiation (*vide* Table XVII, P/Q).

The reaction is always attended with a very large period of induction.

TABLE XIX.

Effect of varying the concentration of glucose.

Region used = $750-600\mu\mu$. HCl = $0.0562N$.

Glucose.	H_2O_2 .	Tungstate.	$I_{\text{abs.}}$	$K_0 \times 10^{10}$.
0.025M	0.0152M	0.02052M	4500 ergs	13.49
0.0125	0.0153M	"	"	11.99
0.00625	"	"	"	10.79
0.025	0.01M	0.01231M	3500	11.40
0.0125	"	"	"	9.59
0.00625	"	"	"	7.19

$1/c_{(\text{glucose})}$ plotted against $1/K$ gives approximately a straight line (Fig. 2).

FIG. 2.

Curves 1 and 2 refer respectively to 0.01231M sol and 0.0205M sol.

TABLE XX.

Effect of varying the concentration of hydrochloric acid.

Region = 750–600 μ . $\text{H}_2\text{O}_2 = 0.00927M$. Chromic tungstate = 0.02052M.

Glucose.	HCl.	I_{abs} .	$K_0 \times 10^{10}$.
0.025M	0.0562N	4500 ergs	13.79
"	0.0390N	"	14.99
"	0.0260N	"	15.59

The velocity constant increases as the concentration of free hydrochloric acid diminishes. It is well known that hydrogen peroxide becomes more stable, the more acid is added to its solution.

Effect of varying the temperature.—The temperature coefficient $\left(\frac{K_T + 10}{K_T}\right)$ is small being of the order of 1.15–1.20.

TABLE XXI.

*Effect of varying the intensity of radiation.*Region = 366 $\mu\mu$. Temp. = 30°.

	<i>I</i> _{abs.}	Glucose.	H ₂ O ₂ .	HCl.	Tungstate.	<i>K</i> _{unimol} × 10 ⁵ .
I.	2030 ergs	0.025 <i>M</i>	0.00927 <i>M</i>	0.0390 <i>N</i>	0.00820 <i>M</i>	5.01
	505	"	"	"	"	2.53
II.	2030	"	0.0121	"	"	5.01
	505	"	"	"	"	2.48

It will be seen from the above table that the velocity constants vary as the square root of the intensity of absorbed radiation in the ultraviolet.

Quantum Efficiency of the Process.—The quantum efficiency of the photo-oxidation was similarly calculated as in Section A. They are given in Tables XVII and XVIII. The quantum efficiency of the photo-oxidation at 366 $\mu\mu$ is always greater than that at 750 $\mu\mu$ —600 $\mu\mu$, as is to be expected. The reaction has the following characteristics :

(1) At 366 $\mu\mu$, for relatively high concentration of H₂O₂, the reaction is zero-molecular with respect to H₂O₂ but for lower concentrations of H₂O₂ it is unimolecular, while at 600 $\mu\mu$ —750 $\mu\mu$ where the absorption is due to chromium atom of the complex, the reaction always obeys the zero-molecular law.

(2) At 366 $\mu\mu$, the velocity of reaction is proportional to the square root of the intensity of absorbed radiation, while at 600—750 $\mu\mu$ (red region) it is directly proportional to the intensity of absorbed radiation.

(3) At 366 $\mu\mu$, quantum efficiency is sometimes greater than unity but at 600 $\mu\mu$ —700 $\mu\mu$ it is always much less than unity, it being much smaller than that at 366 $\mu\mu$.

(4) That inverse of the velocity constant plotted against the inverse of the concentration of the reductant is always a straight line.

It is clear from the above that the chromium pertungstate is simply activated by red light, whereas it is decomposed by a quantum of ultraviolet light.

The reaction mechanism in red light is given thus :—

The whole of the absorbed radiation is available for the activation of chromic pertungstate.

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = K_t \frac{I}{h\nu} \cdot \frac{C_s(G)}{K_2 + K_1 C_s(G)}$$

where $C_s(G)$ is the surface concentration of glucose.

The quantum efficiency must here necessarily be less than unity.

A quantum of ultraviolet radiation, since it is able to start a chain reaction, may give a quantum yield higher than unity as has been actually observed.

$$C_s(G) \text{ is again given by } \frac{K' C^G \text{ Bulk}}{K'' + K' C^G \text{ Bulk}} \quad (\text{Langmuir})$$

which shows that x/c plotted against $1/K$ should be a straight line, as has been experimentally realised.

F. Vanadic Acid Sol as Photosensitiser.

The vanadic acid sol was prepared by the action of acetic acid on sodium vanadate. The p_n value of the sol was determined electrometrically using quinhydrone electrode.

Table XXII shows that a definite quantity of vanadic acid sol liberates the same amount of iodine from KI.

TABLE XXII.

$$\text{NaVO}_3 = 0.033M. \quad \text{Acetic acid} = 0.018M. \quad p_n = 6.0.$$

Time in min.	C. c. thiosulphate (0.003N) = iodine liberated by 0.3 c. c. of the sol solution.
0	2.24
60	2.24
180	2.25
480	2.26

In a mixture of vanadic acid sol and hydrogen peroxide, the total amount of iodine liberated from KI is equivalent to the sum of vanadic acid and hydrogen peroxide.

TABLE XXIII.

H_2O_2 .	$NaVO_3$.	pH of the solution (regulated by acetic acid).	C. c. thiosulphate $\equiv$ iodine liberated by 0.4 c. c. of the mixture.
0.01M	0	5.0	0.85
0	0.033M	5.0	2.72
0.01	0.033	5.9	3.56

There was no dark reaction when hydrogen peroxide, glucose and vanadic acid sol in acid medium containing acetic acid were kept in the dark for 12 hours.

TABLE XXIV.

Effect of varying the concentration of hydrogen peroxide.

$I_{abs.} = 1256$ ergs. Region = 366μ . Temp. = 27° . $d = 1$ cm.

Vanadate.	Acetic acid.	Glucose.	pH .	H_2O_2	K_0 (g. mols transformed in unit time in a unit cell)	Quantum efficiency.
0.033M	0.018M	0.05M	5.0	0.012M	5.17×10^{-10}	1.35
"	"	"	"	0.0156	5.40×10^{-10}	1.41
"	"	"	"	0.023	5.40×10^{-10}	1.41

It will be seen from Table XXIV, that the reaction follows the zero-molecular law with respect to H_2O_2 . The reaction is attended with a large period of induction.

TABLE XXV.

Effect of varying the concentration of glucose.

Temp. = 27° . $I_{abs.} = 1256$ ergs.

Vanadate.	Acetic acid.	Glucose.	pH .	H_2O_2 .	$K_0 \times 10^{10}$.
0.033 M	0.018 N	0.065M	5.0	0.0125M	5.89
"	"	0.05	"	"	5.17
"	"	0.025	"	"	3.62

$1/K$ when plotted against $1/c_{glucose}$ gives a straight line (Fig. 3).

FIG. 3.

Curves 1 and 2 refer respectively to activated and nonactivated sol.

TABLE XXVI.

Effect of varying the concentration of sodium vanadate.

Temp. = 27°. $I_{abs} = 1256$ ergs per cm^2 . per sec.

Vanadate.	μu .	Glucose.	H_2O_2 .	$K_4 \times 10^{10}$.
(a) 0.05M	5.0	0.05 M	0.012 M	5.69
(b) 0.033	5.0	0.05	"	5.17

Under otherwise identical conditions, the velocity constant diminishes very slightly as the concentration of sodium vanadate diminishes.

TABLE XXVII.

Effect of varying the concentration of acetic acid.

Temp. = 28°. $I_{abs} = 4280$ ergs per sq. cm. per sec.

Vanadate.	Acetic acid.	μu .	Glucose.	H_2O_2	$K_4 \times 10^{10}$.
0.033 M	0.036M	4.5	0.025M	0.012M	5.17
"	0.018	5.0	"	"	6.20

The velocity constant diminishes as the p_{H} of the reacting system diminishes.

Temperature Coefficient.—The temperature coefficient is small being of the order of 1.2 – 1.3.

TABLE XXVIII.

Effect of varying the intensity of absorbed radiation.

Temp. = 28°. $\lambda = 366 \mu\mu$.						
I_{abs}	Vanadate.	Acetic acid.	p_{H}	Glucose.	H_2O_2 .	$K_0 \times 10^{10}$.
4280	0.033M	0.018M	5.0	0.025M	0.012M	6.20
1256	"	"	"	"	"	3.62

Table XXVIII shows that the velocity constant is proportional to the square root of absorbed intensity.

Quantum Efficiency of the Process.—Quantum efficiency of the process was calculated as in Section A. γ (Quantum efficiency) is generally greater than unity varying from 1 to 2.

Any mechanism of reaction that may be proposed for this photochemical oxidation should be in a position to explain the following facts:—

- (1) The velocity of reaction is zero-molecular with respect to H_2O_2 .
- (2) The velocity of reaction is proportional to the square root of the intensity of absorbed radiation.
- (3) The quantum efficiency is generally greater than unity, calculated on the assumption that the whole of the absorbed radiation is available for photo-activation.
- (4) That the inverse of velocity constant plotted against the inverse of the concentration of the reductant is a straight line.
- (5) Temperature coefficient is small but of the order of 1.2 – 1.3.

Assuming that the photochemical reaction takes place only between the molecules of glucose and pervanadate adsorbed on the surface of micelles of vanadic acid, and that the mechanism is the same as in the corresponding oxidations by H_2O_2 with tungstic acid as photosensitiser at $366\mu\mu$ (Section A) we arrive at the equation of the velocity of reaction = dx/dt

$$= \sqrt{\frac{I}{K_5 h\nu}} \cdot K_2 C_s [\text{PV}] \frac{K_4 C_G^S}{K_3 + K_4 C_G^S}$$

where $C_s [PVI]$, C_G^B are the surface concentrations of pervanadate and glucose respectively.

It appears that the absorption capacity of vanadic acid micelle for pervanadic acid molecules will always be very large, so that the latter molecules always saturate the surface layer, and we get a zero-molecular velocity constant.

$$\text{Again } C_G = \frac{K_8 C_{Bulk}^B}{K_7 + K_8 C_{Bulk}^B}$$

so that by plotting $1/K$ against $1/c_{bulk}$ we should get a straight line as has been experimentally realised.

Induction Period.—Vanadic acid sol, prepared by the action of acetic acid on sodium vanadate was first exposed to ordinary ultraviolet rays (366 $\mu\mu$) for 4 hours, then immediately mixed with other components of the reacting system and exposed.

TABLE XXIX.

Effect of changing the concentration of H_2O_2 .

Region = 366 $\mu\mu$. Temp. = 26°.

$I_{lim.} = 1027$ ergs. per $cm.^2$ /sec. = 3.1×10^{-10} Einstein.

Na-vanadate.	Acid.	pH .	Glucose.	H_2O_2 .	$K_8 \times 10^{10}$	γ .
0.033M	0.018M	5.0	0.025M	0.03M	4.96	1.60
"	"	"	"	0.0155	4.60	1.48
"	"	"	"	0.0123	4.67	1.50
"	"	"	"	0.009	5.06	1.63

In this reaction with pre-activated sol, induction period which was not prominent before completely disappeared. The velocity of reaction is here again zero-molecular with respect to H_2O_2 , and under similar conditions of experiments the velocities observed are nearly the same as observed with sol not pre-activated.

G. *Chromic Hydroxide Sol as Photosensitiser.*

Preparation of Chromic Hydroxide Sol.—To the boiling chromic chloride solution, powdered ammonium carbonate was added to neutralise the free hydrochloric acid. The addition of ammonium carbonate to the boiling chromic chloride solution was stopped when a small quantity of chromic hydroxide was precipitated. Chromic chloride was then added drop by drop so as to peptise the precipitated chromic hydroxide. During the addition of chromic chloride solution, the liquid was boiled and shaken vigorously. The whole liquid was then dialysed at a temperature of 70°-80°, for 24 hours whereby greenish chromic hydroxide sol was obtained. The p_{π} of the sol was found to be 5.2 with quinhydrone electrode. The reaction does not take place at a much lower value of p_{π} .

No decomposition of hydrogen peroxide was observed in presence of chromic hydroxide sol at 579 $\mu\mu$ when the concentration of hydrogen peroxide was smaller than that of chromic hydroxide. Chromic hydroxide reacts with hydrogen peroxide to form per-compounds. These additive compounds with hydrogen peroxide can not be removed as such by a process of dialysis. Hence it is surmised that the hydrogen peroxide complex remained adsorbed on the micelles of the chromic hydroxide. The dark reaction was found to be negligible.

TABLE XXX.

Region = 579 $\mu\mu$. Temp. = 26°. $I_{abs.} = 800$ ergs.

Glucose.	H ₂ O ₂ .	Chromic hydroxide.	K (unimolecular with respect to H ₂ O ₂).
0.025M	0.015M	0.0211M	12.5 × 10 ⁻⁵
„	0.0113	„	11.32 × 10 ⁻⁵

The above table shows that the reaction is unimolecular with respect to hydrogen peroxide.

H. *Molybdic Acid Sol as Photosensitiser and Ethyl Alcohol as Reductant.*

Reaction with Non-activated Sol.—A mixture of alcohol, hydrogen peroxide, hydrochloric acid and ammonium molybdate does not react when kept in the dark for 10 hours.

TABLE XXXI.

Region = 366 μ .

$I_{abs.} = 1317$ ergs. Ammonium molybdate = 0.05M. HCl = 0.0746N.
EtOH = 4.346M. H₂O₂ = 0.025M. Thiosulphate = 0.01N.

Time in min.	Time interval.	C.c. of thio=0.22 c.c. of reaction mixture.	Titre differ.	$K_0 \times 10^{10}$.
0		1.1		
		7.02 (Induction period)		
60	60	0.9	0.12	7.58 (from 2 & 3)
120	60	0.76	0.14	7.80 (from 2 & 4)
186	66	0.61	0.15	8.11 (from 2 & 5)

From the above table it is clear that there is an induction period at the beginning and it is only after the lapse of this period that the reaction is zero-molecular.

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = K_0 \text{ (expressed in g. mols. transformed per sec. in a unit cell).}$$

This is more clearly brought out by plotting dx/dt against time (Fig 4) The straight portion of the graph after the induction period indicates a constant value of dx/dt .

FIG. 4.

Reaction with Pre-activated Sol.—Here the molybdic acid sol was first exposed to ultraviolet light for a sufficiently long time (about 3 hours) and then mixed immediately with other components of the reacting system. The induction period disappeared in this case.

TABLE XXXII.

All the factors same as in Table XXXI.

	Time in min.	Time interval.	C.c. of thio $\equiv$ 22 c.c. of reaction mixture.	Titre difference.	$K_0 \times 10^{-10}$.
1.	0		1.24		
2.	68	68	1.09	0.15	8.35 (from 1 & 2)
3.	109	41	0.99	0.10	8.69 (from 1 & 3)
4.	203	94	0.78	0.21	8.58 (from 1 & 4)
5.	242	39	0.70	0.08	8.46 (from 1 & 5)

Reactions with pre-activated sol retained the same order (zeromolecular) as in the case of non-activated sol.

TABLE XXXIII.

Effect of varying the concentration of hydrogen peroxide.

$I_{\text{abs.}}$ at $366\mu\mu = 1317 \text{ ergs} = 4.023 \times 10^{-10} \text{ Einstein}$. $\gamma = \text{Quantum efficiency}$. $d = 0.5 \text{ cm}$. $\text{EtOH} = 4.346M$. $\text{Molybdate} = 0.05M$.

H_2O_2 .	HCl.	$K_0 \times 10^{10}$ (non-activated).	γ (non-activated).	$K_0 \times 10^{10}$ (activated).	γ (activated).
0.013M	0.0746N	7.61	0.95	7.95	0.99
0.0157	"	7.35	0.92	7.95	0.99
0.021	"	7.58	0.94	8.03	1.00
0.025	"	7.80	0.97	8.52	1.06

The above table shows that the reaction is zeromolecular with respect to hydrogen peroxide.

TABLE XXXIV,

Effect of varying the concentration of alcohol.

$$I_{\text{abs.}} = 1636.0 \text{ ergs.}$$

Alcohol.	HCl.	Molybdate.	H ₂ O ₂ .	$K_0 \times 10^{10}$ (non-activated).	$K_0 \times 10^{10}$ (activated).
4.346M	0.0746N	0.05M	0.022M	9.8	10.6
2.173	"	"	"	7.52	7.94
1.087	"	"	"	5.19	5.43

$1/K$ graphically plotted against $1/c$ (alcohol) gives a straight line (Fig. 5).

FIG. 5.

Curves 1 and 2 refer respectively to non-activated and activated sol.

TABLE XXXV.

Effect of varying the concentration of hydrochloric acid.

HCl.	Molybdate.	H ₂ O ₂ .	Alcohol.	$I_{\text{abs.}}$	$K_0 \times 10^{10}$.
0.297N	0.05M	0.021M	4.346M	1317 ergs	4.96
0.148	"	"	"	"	5.07
0.0746	"	"	"	"	7.58
0.05	"	"	"	"	8.48

TABLE XXXVI.

Effect of varying the concentration of molybdate.

Molybdate.	H ₂ O ₂	Alcohol.	p_H .	$I_{abs.} (Q)$.	$K_0 \times 10^{10}$.	$K/Q \times 10^{10}$.
0.05M	0.027M	4.346	2.7	1636 ergs.	10.10	6.18
0.025	"	"	"	1365	8.35	6.12

The velocity of reaction is practically independent of the molybdic acid sol.

TABLE XXXVII.

Effect of varying the intensity of radiation.

$I_{abs.}$	Alcohol.	HCl.	Molybdate.	H ₂ O ₂ .	$K_0 \times 10^{10}$.
1404.8	4.326M	0.0746N	0.05M	0.025M	8.45
724.3	"	"	"	"	4.66
1404.8	"	"	"	0.022	8.07
724.3	"	"	"	"	4.39

The zeromolecular velocity constant is directly proportional to the intensity of absorbed radiation.

Quantum Efficiency of the Process.—The quantum efficiency of the reaction is of the order of unity.

Temperature Coefficient.—The temperature coefficient $\left(\frac{K_T + 10}{K_T}\right)$ is of the order of unity.

The photochemical reactions described in this section have the following characteristic features :—

- (1) The reaction is zeromolecular with respect to H₂O₂.
- (2) The reaction is independent of the concentration of molybdic acid sol.
- (3) With the increase in the concentration of the reductant, the velocity constant increases, $1/K$ plotted against $1/c$ gives a straight line.

- (4) The temperature coefficient of the reaction is unity.
- (5) The quantum efficiency is approximately unity.

The whole of the absorbed radiation is available for the activation of molecules of permolybdate absorbed on the surface of micelles of molybdic acid.

The rate of reaction between the activated permolybdate molecules and the alcohol molecules is given by

$$I/h\nu = K_2[\text{PM}]_{\text{active}} + K_3[\text{PM}]_{\text{active}} C_n^s$$

where C_n^s is the surface concentration of reductant (alcohol).

Hence
$$[\text{PM}]_{\text{active}} = \frac{\frac{I}{h\nu}}{K_2 + K_3 C_n^s}$$

$$dx/dt = K \cdot \frac{I}{h\nu} \cdot \frac{C_n^s}{K_2 + K_3 C_n^s}$$

Now $C_n^s = \frac{K' C_n^b}{K'' + K' C_n^b}$ where C_n^b is the bulk concentration of the reductant.

For large values of C_n^b , C_n^s is large and in the limiting case the factor

$\frac{K' C_n^b}{K'' + K' C_n^b}$ becomes unity. Then we have $\frac{dx}{dt} = \frac{I}{h\nu}$ and the quantum

efficiency of the reaction is unity.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Again normally, } dt/dx &= \frac{hv}{I} \cdot \frac{K_2 + K_3 C_R^s}{K \cdot C_R^s} \\ &= \frac{hv}{I} \cdot \frac{I}{C_R^s} + K_3 \end{aligned}$$

Under otherwise identical conditions, the inverse of velocity constant plotted against inverse of the concentration of reductant should give a straight line as has been experimentally observed.

In conclusion I would like to express my thanks to Prof. J. C. Chosh for his kind interest in the work and to the Director of Public Instruction, Bengal for his kindly awarding me a Bengal Government Research Scholarship which enabled me to carry out this piece of investigation.

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